

EVALUATION OF APACHE SUPERSET

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The main objective of this project is to explore what Apache Superset is, what benefits it offers, how to get started with it, and what makes the Superset platform unique from its alternatives.

The main steps in this project are:

1. Getting familiarized with the CERN Cloud infrastructure and the Kubernetes Service in CERN
2. Configuration of Apache Superset
3. Containerizing an instance of Superset
4. Deployment of the containerized instance in DIR Kubernetes clusters
5. Creating Helm charts for Kubernetes deployment.
6. Comparison of the functionalities of both BI tool

ABSTRACT

Business intelligence is a process that uses technology and data science to convert raw data to meaningful information and knowledge for businesses to help them make profitable data-driven decisions. At CERN, Pentaho Enterprise Edition is used as a business intelligence tool by different teams for different purposes such as creating financial reports, invoices, enterprise asset management reports, access control reports and it is even used for CERN badge printing and other different purposes.

The aim of this project is to explore possible alternatives for license free business intelligence and data visualization tools that can replace Pentaho Enterprise Edition. In the scope of this, Apache Superset is explored and evaluated. Required configurations and dependencies are investigated and implemented. Then, a containerized installation of a Superset instance is deployed in the Kubernetes clusters of the Data Integration and Reporting team. As a last step, the functionalities of Apache Superset are compared with the existing Pentaho stack.

Apache Superset is a powerful open source business intelligence tool with a data visualization and exploration platform that can meet up most of the needs of end users at CERN. On top of that it is highly-scalable and cloud native.

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1 WHAT IS APACHE SUPERSET?

Apache Superset is an open source, enterprise-ready, easy-to-use business intelligence web application. It is a data visualization and exploration platform which enables users to query datasets, create charts and generate dashboards. Superset was first started, in 2015, as a hackathon project at Airbnb. One year later, in 2016, it was open-sourced and joined the Apache Incubator program. In 2021, the first official release of Superset 1.0 was announced by Apache Software Foundation. Since then, it has been serving as a fully customizable application to visualize and explore large amounts of data in a fast and intuitive way. Nowadays, Superset has become a highly preferred cloud-native alternative to other well known BI tools such as Power BI, Tableau, Looker and many others.

2 FEATURES OF APACHE SUPERSET

Superset has many useful features. In this part, these features will be covered.

2.1 Web Interface

Superset offers an intuitive and easy-to-use interface for visualizing datasets and designing interactive dashboards. Navigation through different features and tools is simple and doesn't require any expertise.

2.2 No Coding Skills

Superset doesn't require any coding skills. It is designed for people who do not know how to code. Non-programmers like business analysts and financial analysts can easily use this business intelligence tool if they have a basic understanding of SQL.

2.3 Data Visualization

Superset provides a wide variety of different and rich visualization types to showcase data. It is possible to create complex charts and interactive dashboards using geo-spatial visualizations, pivot tables, sankey diagrams and many other particular chart types. The chart building process is built on a drag drop environment. This feature helps to explore data in a much easier way. With Superset, it is also allowed to add custom visualization plugins and enhance their capabilities.

2.4 Charts and Interactive Dashboards

Superset enables the users to create interactive dashboards where the users can apply a variety of filters to the charts present within a dashboard to get more detailed information and a better understanding of the data. Charts and dashboards can easily be shared via a simple URL.

2.5 Database Connectivity

Superset provides integration with most SQL-speaking databases through SQLAlchemy. It requires a Python DB-API database driver and a SQLAlchemy dialect to be installed for each datastore you want to connect to. Superset doesn't provide any support for NoSQL databases.

2.6 SQL Editor and Querying

Superset lets users run SQL queries on the SQL Lab to investigate their data. SQL Lab is a modern SQL IDE for detailed analysis of the data. It lets the users integrate and analyze their data quickly, write and run real-time queries on live data rapidly, visualize the results of the queries as charts and view database metadata such as tables, columns, indexes, partitions. It is also possible to save the query for future purposes. Superset also provides support for long-running queries. Celery distributed queues are used to dispatch the queries to worker nodes and a “results backend” can be defined to persist the long-running query results.

2.7 Semantic Layer

A semantic layer is a business abstraction layer provided for business users to better understand the data without getting lost in the technical complexity. It enables the users to quickly discover and access data. Superset offers a thin semantic layer that can store two types of computed data: metrics and calculated columns. Virtual metrics are composed by aggregating values from columns such as the sum or average of a column. Virtual calculated metrics are the extensions of a table that is calculated with a formula for each row. Superset also enables the user to create a virtual dataset from the database source. Virtual datasets are views of the data and they can be constructed by the users by using JOIN and other SQL commands using the SQL IDE.

2.8 Authentication

Superset is built on top of the Flask App builder (FAB) and it provides integration with major authentication backends (database, OpenID, LDAP, OAuth, REMOTE_USER, etc).

2.9 Data Security and Roles

Superset provides a security model that gives the users total control over the accessibility of their data. Different users can be given different levels of access, different roles can be customized for different users. It empowers the user to configure rules on who can access which product features and datasets and track their behavior. This makes it easier to assign roles/permission and to manage the application smoothly. Superset provides different types of roles (three are major roles - admin, alpha, and gamma roles, each with a different level of access).

2.10 Sharing and Collaboration

Sharing Superset charts and dashboards with others and collaborating on data analysis works is straightforward. Permalinks can easily be created and sent to others for sharing the visualizations. Superset also provides setting up of event-triggered notifications (alerts) and scheduled notifications (reports). Alerts are custom links to charts and dashboards and they are triggered when an event occurs. An event occurs when an SQL condition is reached. Alerts are delivered via e-mails or Slack notifications. Reports are the snapshots of a dashboard or a chart and it runs on previously defined schedules. These reports are also delivered via emails or Slack notifications.

2.11 Scalability

Superset was designed to be cloud native meaning it is highly scalable and flexible. It can be run in lightweight containers and also scaled out to large and distributed environments. For example Superset is run in Airbnb's production environment inside Kubernetes and serves more than 600 daily active users viewing over 100000 charts a day.

2.12 API Documentation

Superset provides a REST API that follows the OpenAPI Specification. It provides the most relevant endpoints of Superset.

3 SUPERSET INSTALLATION AND CONFIGURATION

There are a couple ways to install and get started with Superset:

1. The source code can be downloaded from Apache Foundation's website and set up locally
2. Superset python package can be downloaded from Pypi using a python virtual environment
3. Superset can be locally set up using Docker Compose
4. Superset Docker image can be downloaded from Docker Hub and installed in a Docker container
5. Kubernetes can be used to deploy an instance of Superset
6. Official Helm charts can be downloaded and run

In this project, a customized Superset Docker image is created based on the official Superset Docker image and then it is installed inside the DIR team's Kubernetes clusters. This part of the report is to provide information about the architecture, to share guidelines for the installation and explanation of the configurations.

3.1 Internal Architecture and Technology Stack

Apache Superset is entirely built on Python and Flask in the backend and Javascript in the frontend. It uses Flask App Builder internally which is a modular web application development framework to build web services in python.

Superset has its own metadata database, which can be configured but by default it is SQLite, in which it stores its metadata such as information about users, permissions, information about created dashboards or saved requests.

There is an async part of the Superset infrastructure. This part is to deal with the fact that multiple web servers are expected to run a web request, coming from different clients. These web requests are expected to time out at about 30 seconds to 60 seconds. But most of the analytics type queries last much longer than this, for minutes or hours possibly. As a solution to this timeout problem, web servers can be configured to time out after a longer period of time. But this solution is not the best practice. The best practice would be to set up an optional async infrastructure. In this solution, the main superset application doesn't

execute user requests itself. The web server adds the query tasks in a message queue (Redis). Celery worker nodes can monitor this queue, execute the tasks and update the database. The main application can then render the result to the user. This way long running queries can be executed without timeouts.

For caching, Superset uses Flask Caching by default. Caching is very useful if there are thousands of users looking at the same dashboard every day which are the results of some expensive queries. By using caching, expensive queries are run only for the first time. When the queries get the results, they are stored in the cache so that when other users want to see the same dashboard, they won't have to execute the same queries. They will get the results from the cache. Also there are lots of functionalities around warming up the cache and invalidating the cache when new data comes in.

It is very much scalable. You can have as many instances as you want depending on the load you want to handle. It is also very much extensible that you can use different technologies for different deployment strategies. It is supported with different deployment frameworks.

3.2 Configuration

Superset has a flexible architecture. It can be set up differently for different production environments according to their needs.

To configure Superset, the only step to take is to define the specifics of the Superset application in a python file named “superset_config.py” and add it to the “SUPERSET_CONFIG_PATH”. Superset source code contains a configuration python file called “config.py” which has all the default settings. At the end of this python file, “SUPERSET_CONFIG_PATH” is checked if there is a file named “superset_config.py” that exists in the “SUPERSET_CONFIG_PATH”. This way the default configurations can be overridden. This configuration file is a fully functional python file so methods etc. can be added to that file.

There are many features of Superset that you can customize according to your needs and preferences. You can select the web server, metadata database, caching layer, authentication, message queue and results backend according to your business needs.

1. **Web Server:** There are multiple web server options that Superset can run on such as Gunicorn, NGINX, Apache etc. however running on Gunicorn in async mode is highly recommended. Because Gunicorn web server is built to scale up with the increasing requests. Async mode is recommended because of the possible long running analytics queries. In order to use Gunicorn as the web server, “gevent” Python library needs to be installed. After the installation, the configuration parameters can be defined in the “superset_config.py”.
2. **Metadata Database:** Superset has SQLite by default as the metadata database. But other databases can also be used instead of SQLite. In order to use other databases, first the SQLAlchemy dialect and Python driver of this database should be installed. For this project, PostgreSQL is used as a metadata database and the “psycopg2” and other operating system libraries are installed for this. After the installation, a database and a user need to be defined to store metadata and access it. Connection string should be added to the “superset_config.py” file under the “SQLALCHEMY_DATABASE_URI” variable. Other configurations regarding Postgres can be made using the “pg_hba.conf” file. Then the setup of PostgreSQL as the metadata database will be complete.
3. **Caching:** For caching purposes Superset uses Flask caching, by default. Any caching backends can be used, including Redis, Memcached, SimpleCache. For this project, Redis

is used for caching. “redis” python package is installed and the necessary configurations are done in the configuration file under the variable “CACHE_CONFIG”.

4. **Long Running Queries:** Some clients may run analytics queries that can last minutes or hours. Those queries are not usually complete within the lifetime of a web request. As a result these queries cause a request timeout. To overcome this situation, Superset handles these long running analytics queries using asynchronous working Celery workers and queues. Superset recommends using Redis for the message queue. A results backend is also needed to persist the query results. For this, “RESULT_BACKEND” variable should be set in the configuration file.
5. **Securing Data:** To secure the session data exchanged between the client and the Superset web server, sensitive information should be encrypted. Therefore a strong secret key should be generated and added to the configuration file under the variable “SECRET_KEY”.

3.3 Dockerfile

A docker image of Superset is present in Docker Hub which only contains a base Superset build. Therefore, based on this Docker image, a simple Dockerfile is created. In this Dockerfile:

1. Database drivers are installed to be used as analytics and metadata database
2. A local admin account is created using Flask Application Builder
3. Local databases are upgraded
4. Example datasets are loaded
5. Superset roles and permissions are set up
6. “superset_config.py” file is copied into the container and the path is given to the environment variable “SUPERSET_CONFIG_PATH”
7. 8088 port is exposed

3.4 Automation via GitLab CI

Using GitLab CI, the creation of the Docker image from the Dockerfile is automated. For this, Kaniko image builder is used. Kaniko is a tool to build container images from a Dockerfile, inside a container or Kubernetes cluster. With this automated job, building a new Docker image and storing it in the Gitlab registry is automated. So, whenever a change is made in the Dockerfile, a new image is automatically built and stored in GitLab registry

3.5 Deployment with Kubernetes

Kubernetes is a system for operating, deploying, managing and orchestrating containerized applications at scale. For deployment, a containerized installation of an Apache Superset is run in DIR’s Kubernetes Infrastructure, under a separate namespace.

To deploy an instance of Superset, first a secret file is created. A secret in Kubernetes is an object that contains sensitive data such as a password, a token or a key. In this case, the

secret contains the token to access the Superset image generated by Gitlab and stored in the Gitlab registry.

After the creation of the secret file, a deployment file is created. Deployment objects describe, to Kubernetes, how to create and modify instances of the containerized application and the desired state of a deployment. With deployment objects, pods can be created. Pods are the smallest unit of deployment. In this deployment file below information are indicated:

1. namespace to deploy in (metadata.namespace)
2. number of replicated pods (spec.replicas)
3. container name (spec.template.spec.containers.name)
4. image name (spec.template.spec.containers.image)
5. container port (spec.template.spec.containers.ports.containerPort)
6. imagePullSecrets (spec.template.spec.imagePullSecrets)

To be able to access the application, Service objects are created in Kubernetes to expose the application running in a Pod as a network service. With services, Kubernetes gives an IP address to the pods.

3.6 Deployment Using Helm Charts

The reason for using Helm charts is that Helm is a tool for deployment of services and applications to Kubernetes clusters and makes deployment of services and applications to Kubernetes clusters much easier. With Helm, there is no need to write separate yaml files for applications. For deployment with Helm, necessary configurations are done in the “values.yaml” file. With a single "install" command, deployment is possible.

4 SUPERSET COMPARISON WITH PENTAHO

Pentaho is a business intelligence tool that is being used at CERN by different teams for different purposes such as creating financial reports, invoices, enterprise asset management reports, access control reports, CERN badge printing and other different purposes.

Pentaho has two different subscription models: community edition and enterprise edition. At CERN, both the community edition and the enterprise edition of Pentaho are used by several users to create interactive reports, dashboards and analyzer reports. In this section of the report, the difference between the community edition and the enterprise edition of Pentaho will be explained. Also the Superset features that can replace the community edition features will be discussed.

4.1 Pentaho Community vs. Enterprise Edition

Pentaho offers more advanced functionalities for the enterprise edition users. The main components that the enterprise edition offers are: interactive reporting, analyzer and dashboard designer.

1. **Interactive Reporting:** The drag-and-drop interface of Pentaho Enterprise Edition helps mainly to create visualizations and generate reports very quickly by adding new elements and notes and publishing them.
2. **Analyzer:** Analyzer gives the user the ability to query data, filter data and visualize data using tables, histograms, geo maps or heat grids. It is also possible to limit the data in a report by using filters. With the filters, it is possible to see only the requested data you want to view and discard the unnecessary data
3. **Dashboard View:** With Dashboard View, it is possible to gather the reports and graphs that have been done with the analyzer and pull them all into a dashboard view to create high-level visualizations.

The functionalities that these components offer can also be provided by Apache Superset.

1. **Datasources and Querying:** With Superset, it is possible to query data from a database or a datasource and save the queried and filtered data as a new dataset. Superset offers the SQL Lab view for this purpose. With SQL Lab, it is possible to add, view, edit, delete and share queries. It is also possible to upload CSV files as datasets. Figure 1.
2. **Charts and Visualization:** After creating the dataset, users can create a table view of the data or any other visualizations. To create a chart, the first step is to choose the dataset that is going to be used. After that, an “Explore” view will be opened and in this window, users can explore and interpret the data, create charts and then dashboards using these charts. On the left hand side, below the “Chart Source”, the metrics and the columns are visible. By dragging and dropping these metrics and columns to the section in the middle, the required chart can be created in the section on the right hand side. Any filtering of the data can be done under the “Filtering” tab. Figure 2.
3. **Pivot Tables:** With Superset, it is possible to create pivot tables as well as table charts. Pivot tables are an interactive way to calculate and summarize large amounts of data. With pivot tables it is possible to create interactive reports. Pivot tables allow aggregating individual values into a more extensive table with discrete categories. The present data in the table can be filtered out or sorted out according to the needs. Figure 3.
4. **Dashboards and Filtering:** Another functionality of Superset is that users can create dashboards with the charts that they created. Charts can be used to create new dashboards from scratch or they can also be added to the existing dashboards. The view of a dashboard can be edited and reorganized. A specific refresh rate can be set for each dashboard to automatically refresh the data present in the table. Refreshing can also be done manually for each chart in the dashboard.

Dashboards can be customized according to the user needs. Headers can be added to emphasize titles. Dividers can be used to separate charts from each other physically. Different tabs can be created within a dashboard for segmenting the charts into different groups. A markdown box can be used to add texts and images.

Another important functionality is that filters can be applied to the charts in dashboards. Five different types of filters can be applied to the data in a dashboard: value, numerical range, time range, time column and time grain. To begin, first the dataset and the column in the data that the filter is going to be applied to, should be selected. Then the filtering type should be selected.

Value filter type is to select specific values of a certain column to display data. With the numerical range filter type, it is possible to specify a certain numerical range for numerical data. Time range filter type is to specify a certain range of time of a time column. Time column filter type is to overwrite the previously selected time column defined for the chart with the newly selected time column option. With the time grain option, a time granularity (minute, hour, day, month, year . . .) is set to group the data according to the selected time grain.

Cross-filtering is also possible, meaning that a filter can be applied to a chart and the selected data group can be used as a filter for all the other charts in the dashboard.

When the dashboard is complete, a permalink can be created and shared with others. Figure 4.

Figure 1: Dataset View

Figure 2: Explore View

Figure 3: Pivot Table

4.2 Authentication and Permission

In Superset, security is handled by the Flask Application Builder. FAB provides authentication, user management, permissions and roles. User management is handled by roles. Roles are templates of permission sets which are applied to users to manage permissions and restrictions. Not all the users need to have the same permissions and restrictions while using Superset. For example, for users who need to execute similar tasks, like viewing the same dashboards or executing the same queries, a common role can be defined and this role can be assigned to each user.

There are five roles pre-defined by Superset.

1. **Admins:** Admin users have control over all the charts and dashboards. They can modify all the charts and dashboards present in the database. Admins also have all the possible rights, like granting rights to other users or revoking rights from other users. Admin users have the permission to add a database and data sources.
2. **Alpha Role:** Alpha users have access to all data sources, they can add or remove data sources. But they cannot grant or revoke access from other users. They are also limited to alter the objects they own.
3. **Gamma Role:** Gamma users have limited access. They are not able to add or alter any datsource. They can only use the data coming from the database that they have access to. Also they can only see the charts and dashboards made from the datsource that they have access to. It is recommended to give a user the Gamma role plus any other role that would add access to specific data sources.
4. **SqlLab Role:** This role grants access to the sql ide, the SQL Lab. By default admin users have access to all databases but both Gamma and Alpha users need to be given permission on a per database basis.
5. **Public Role:** This role is useful when you want to enable logged out anonymous users to view a dashboard.

Figure 4: Dashboard View

Possible permissions that can be assigned to users and roles are as follows:

1. **Model & Action:** Models are entities like charts, dashboards for users and each model has a fixed set of permissions like can edit or can delete. For example you can allow a user to delete a dashboard by simply giving a role “can_delete” permission on the dashboard entity and then assign this role to the user.
2. **View Permission:** Views are web pages like Charts, Dashboards, SQL Lab. When granted, the user will see that view in the menu items above and be able to load that page.
3. **Datasource Permission:** It is possible with Superset to create a permission to access to each datasource. Users only see the charts and dashboards of the datasource that are granted to them.
4. **Database Permission:** You can grant the user access to a database and that way the user can access all datasources within the database. Access to the charts and dashboards of this database will still require extra permission.

New roles can be created following Settings > Security > List Roles and clicking on + sign. From this window you can create new roles and assign permissions to these roles. Figure 5.

5 CONCLUSION

This project’s aim is to explore new and alternative business intelligence tools to replace the enterprise version of Pentaho which is used at CERN for different reporting purposes. In this project, I worked with Apache Superset which is an open source and free BI tool, to see if it would be a good solution to substitute Pentaho. During this project, a proof of concept containerized installation of an Apache Superset instance is produced and run on the Kubernetes Infrastructure of the CERN Data Integration and Reporting team. Necessary configurations

Figure 5: List of Roles

and dependencies are discussed and implemented for deployment. Finally a comparison of functionalities between the enterprise edition of Pentaho and Apache Superset is made.

With this comparison, it is clearly visible that Superset is able to meet most of the functionalities that Pentaho enterprise edition is offering. In addition, Superset offers more convenient functionalities that can streamline and enhance the user-experience as well as facilitating and maintaining the application for the CERN IT-DIR department.

A favorable future step will be to allow the end-users at CERN to use Apache Superset and learn about their user experiences and see if it is meeting up their demands. After that it is also possible to compare and evaluate Apache Superset with the community editions of the well-known BI tools like Tableau or Power BI.

6 REFERENCES

1. “Introduction: Superset.” Superset Documentation, The Apache Software Foundation, <https://superset.apache.org/docs/intro>.
2. “Preset User Documentation.” Preset User Documentation, Preset, <https://docs.preset.io/>.
3. Shekhar, Shashank. Apache Superset Quick Start Guide. Packt Publishing Ltd., 2018, O’Reilly, <https://www.oreilly.com/library/view/apache-superset-quick/9781788992244/>, Accessed 2022.

